

Validity and Reliability Test Results of Octalysis Core Drive Questionnaire for Requirement Change Management

The following Table 1 presents a summary of the validity test (item–total correlations) and reliability test (Cronbach’s Alpha) for each core drive construct in the perception questionnaire. All tests were conducted with N=32 respondents.

Table 1. Summary of Validity and Reliability Test Results for Core Drive Questionnaire

Core Drive	Number of Items	Item–Total Correlation (r)	Sig. (p)	Cronbach’s Alpha	Remarks
CD1 (Epic Meaning & Calling)	4	0.710 – 0.768	<0.05	0.718	Valid & Reliable
CD2 (Development & Accomplishment)	6	0.715 – 0.809	<0.05	0.833	Valid & Reliable
CD3 (Empowerment of Creativity & Feedback)	5	0.707 – 0.782	<0.05	0.81	Valid & Reliable
CD4 (Ownership & Possession)	4	0.761 – 0.907	<0.05	0.84	Valid & Reliable
CD5 (Social Influence & Relatedness)	6	0.716 – 0.788	<0.05	0.84	Valid & Reliable
CD6 (Scarcity & Impatience)	4	0.741– 0.822	<0.05	0.79	Valid & Reliable
CD7 (Unpredictability & Curiosity)	5	0.816 – 0.902	<0.01	0.911	Valid & Reliable
CD8 (Loss & Avoidance)	4	0.743 – 0.841	<0.05	0.775	Valid & Reliable

Notes:

- All items within each core drive showed significant correlations with their respective total construct scores ($p < 0.05$), thus meeting the validity criteria [1].
- Cronbach’s Alpha values for all constructs were above 0.70, which indicates satisfactory internal reliability [2], [3].

- Accordingly, the core drive perception questionnaire can be considered valid and reliable for subsequent analysis in this study, and the psychometric properties align with recommended practices for instrument validation in behavioural and organisational research.

I. References

- [1] J. F. Hair, W. C. Black, B. J. Babin, and R. E. Anderson, *Multivariate Data Analysis*, 8th ed. Boston, MA: Cengage Learning, 2019.
- [2] J. C. Nunnally and I. H. Bernstein, *Psychometric Theory*, 3rd ed. New York: McGraw-Hill, 1994.
- [3] M. Tavakol and R. Dennick, 'Making sense of Cronbach's alpha', *International Journal of Medical Education*, vol. 2, pp. 53–55, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.5116/ijme.4dfb.8dfd>